

CoPropel

Composite material technology for next-generation Marine Vessel Propellers

www.Copropel.com

Deliverable Number	D6.2
Deliverable title	Initial plan for dissemination and exploitation, including communication activities
Lead beneficiary	TWI
Version	V1
Number of pages	21
Due date of deliverable	30/11/2022
Actual submission date	30/11/2022
Type	R = Document, report
Dissemination level	PU = Public

GA number: 101056911

Start Date: 01/06/2022

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Revision history of the document

Rev. version	Date	Description of modification	Authors /Reviewers
V0.1	04 Nov 2022	Initial Draft	Nithin Jayasree, TWI
V0.2	21 Nov 2022	Market survey	Paul Jones, Nithin Jayasree TWI
V0.3	28 Nov 2022	Revision	Tsirka Kyriaki
V0.4	30 Nov 2022	Updated draft	Nithin Jayasree, TWI
V1	30 Nov 2022	Final version ready to submit	Nithin Jayasree, TWI

Distribution list

Partner n°	Name of beneficiary (short name)	Person's Name	Country
1	University of Ioannina (Uoi)	Tsirka Kyriaki, Paipetis Alkiviadis	Greece
2	Danaos Shipping Company Limited (DAN)	Fotis Oikonomou	Cyprus
3	Bureau Veritas (BV)	Stephane Paboeuf	France
4	MECA	Marion LARREUR	France
5	Loiretech (LT)	Franck Bourcier	France
6	Bulgarian Ship Hydrodynamics Centre (BSHC)	Rumen Kishev	Bulgaria
7	Glafcos Marine Ltd (GME)	Leonidas Drikos	Greece
8	TWI Limited (TWI)	Nithin Jayasree	United Kingdom
9	Brunel University London (BUL)	Aldyandra HamiSeon	United Kingdom

Contents

Revision history of the document.....	3
Distribution list.....	3
Glossary.....	5
1. Introduction	6
1.1. Deliverable Objectives	7
2. Communication strategy.....	8
2.1. Communication activities.....	8
2.2. Approval/objection process of communication activities	10
2.3. Promotion channels	10
2.4. Policy for communication material.....	10
2.5. Branding policy.....	11
2.6. Public website and social media	11
2.7. Mailing lists	13
2.8. Logo.....	13
3. Dissemination and exploitation strategy	14
3.1. Dissemination and exploitation objectives.....	15
3.2. Exploitation content.....	15
4. Market outlook	16
4.1. Status of target markets:	16
Marine freight shipping.....	16
Status of target markets: Shipbuilding.....	16
4.2. The influence of policy and regulation.....	17
CO2 reduction	17
Noise reduction.....	17
Qualification and certification of composite propellers	17
5. Competitive landscape.....	18
5.1. Supply chain and market entry points	18
6. Competitive landscape.....	19
7. Porter – five forces analysis	20
References	21

Glossary

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOA	Description of action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Fair Accessible Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
OA	Open Access
OS	Open Science
PDC	Project Data Contact
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
WP	Work Package
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturers

1. Introduction

CoPropel puts forth a holistic approach towards the realisation of marine propellers made of advanced composite materials. Compared to their traditional counterparts, marine composite propellers offer efficiency gains in propulsion efficiency, noise reduction and weight savings.

The CoPropel project will see an interdisciplinary team of experts drawn both from research and industry, from theoretical considerations and numerical modelling to precision manufacturing - assembly and experimental verification testing. The CoPropel action brings together 9 organisations from 5 countries: 4 Research Institutes – TWI, University of Ioannina, Brunel University London and The Bulgarian Ship Hydrodynamics Centre; 4 Industrial partners – Loiretech, MECA, Danaos and Glafcos Marine with one certification body Bureau Veritas Marine & Offshore. Together, we will develop and bring to market a marine composite propeller with an embedded structural health monitoring system. The proposed activities will mature our Technology Readiness Level to 5-6 and drastically de-risk the integration of the investigated solutions on future products, effectively resulting in reducing the direct operating costs for the operators while minimizing the environmental impact.

Existing work by the partners has shown an approximate 12% reduction in energy consumption and subsequent fuel consumption, with the potential savings exceeding 15% at full-scale marine vessel propellers, which will be investigated and confirmed during our real-time sea trials as part of the CoPropel project.

The main objectives of the project are summarized in Table 1

Table 1 List of Objectives for the CoPropel

No	Objectives	Objective description and means of verification
1	Design a large scale composite marine propeller utilising methodologies and composite materials	The key characteristic of composite materials is the capability to exploit their inherent anisotropy in order to tailor the stiffness and strength of the final product. This will enable the propeller blades to exhibit outstanding hydrodynamic efficiency as well as controlled deformations pertaining to shape-adaptive structures capable of adapting their shape according to the specific regime of the operational envelope. The design activities of the composite propeller are planned for the first 24 months of the project, with a Critical Design Review (CDR) performed at the end of the second year of the project. More precisely, three different CDRs will be performed which will focus on the following items: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CDR for the blades in M21 (6 months before the final CDR in order to start full scale manufacturing) 2. CDR for root and fixing in M24 3. CDR for SHM system together with final assessment of full propeller in M27
2	Optimise the manufacturing process for the fabrication of the composite propeller based on closed mould resin infusion techniques.	Resin infusion/injection techniques are particularly suitable for such structures. Together with the unique process monitoring and online quality control technologies available at the consortium level, they guarantee repeatability and quality assurance at every step of the manufacturing process. Automation processes will be built into the manufacturing system in order to allow increased productivity and error elimination. The novel manufacturing process will be approved through a CDR in M21 which will

		focus on the blades of the propeller. In that way, the outside surface will be fixed and the RTM tools can start getting prepared 6 months before the final CDR which will be done in M27.
3	Develop a condition and structural health monitoring system that will be embedded within the propeller	A network of suitable sensors will be embedded within the propeller structure and transmit information about the “structural health” of the composite structure. This Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) system, apart from the embedded sensors, will be comprised of signal transmission lines, interrogators, and analysis modules that will enable the detection of events such as impacts with objects as well as the identification of inspection and repair intervals. The SHM system will be fully developed and assessed at the CDR on M24 of the project.
4	Validation of the composite propeller	Precursor testing of smaller-scale (1:5) propeller demonstrator will be carried out in the relevant environment, e.g. water tank, in order to de-risk the full-scale testing (WP4). Then, validation testing of a full-scale propeller with a 1.5m–1.8m diameter (to be defined based on the available vessel) in a real environment (sea trials) will be conducted. The composite propeller along with the SHM system will be installed in a marine vessel and tested in real operational conditions (WP5). With these 6-month trials, TRL 7 of the technology will be achieved. Sea trials will take place at the end of the project (M30 to M35), and the experimental data will be compared with predictions.
5	Assist in the formulation of new guidelines regarding the use of composite materials at the propeller	Our consortium partner BV is developing a guidance note NI663 concerning the design assessment of propeller in composites materials. In order to complete and improve this document, BV will use results obtained in the project with regards to <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. the design assessment methods and fatigue investigation, 2. the manufacturing survey, 3. the propeller monitoring 4. the testing procedure including the quality control.
6	Communication and Dissemination of the project outcomes – open science-related objective	CoPropel will be widely promoted across different academic and industrial stakeholders by providing at least 6 open access scientific publications. Within the scope of the project, we will identify and attend at least 4 major Marine and Composite Conferences and Events that will serve as communication channels to promote CoPropel.
7	Define roll out strategy and develop a business plan	Future technical and business development roadmaps will be defined and be available at the consortium level towards the end of the project. Certification issues are the focus of specific activities, and the foreground knowledge during the project's tenure will simplify future applications.

1.1. Deliverable Objectives

This deliverable describes the communication and dissemination plan of the results from the CoPropel project. The dissemination and exploitation activities will be presented, focusing on reaching the relevant market/end users. This is the sixth objective for the CoPropel project as presented in **Table 1**

2. Communication strategy

2.1. Communication activities

The strategy that will be followed for the communication and promotion of the CoPropel project and its results, includes an efficient and effective mix of both interpersonal and mass communication tools. Moreover, care will be taken that, for each targeted audience, a distinct strategy using appropriate messages, means and language has been planned for. Namely, specific audiences and communication methods have been defined for promoting CoPropel and its main results, as summarised in **Table 2**.

Table 2 Communication strategy

Communication activity	Target audience
Attendance at seminars and conferences, one-to-one communication, e-mailing stakeholders, periodic newsletters as direct communication means.	Expert audience in composite engineering and technology and relative manufacturing technologies
Contacting parallel related projects, cross-field events.	Expert audience in the marine composites and structural sensors community that includes academic, engineering and business developing personnel as well as EC personnel .
General communication through the Project website, press releases, posters and leaflets .	General public and experts .
Publications in highly-ranked journals, presentations at conferences.	Academic personnel and industrial experts in the field of composite materials manufacturing and automation
Conveyance of the new knowledge into University curriculums, publications of MSc and PhD theses.	Academic personnel and engineering students as well as industrial experts.

The communication of the project outcomes will be carried out in the following ways:

- **Conferences and Exhibitions:** The project will utilise the CoPropel grant to have exhibition stands and/or oral and poster presentations at a number of major European and international seminars, workshops, conferences and trade fairs for the presentation of project results and a prototype demonstration to potential partners and end users and development of a potential sales pipeline.
- **Project website and social media:** The website will be used for the dissemination of information about the project and the individual collaborators to all stakeholders and the general public. A project website will facilitate the internal information flow between partners and with a public section for general dissemination. In addition, we shall promote the technology using social media tools, such as LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook for project updates.
- **Electronic and printed material:** Results and reports will be communicated by mail, email, a dedicated protected project website and via the planned project meetings. Suitable dissemination materials in a range of standard formats (electronic and printed) for distribution through targeted campaigns of mail, email and web will be produced. Activities will include:
 - Press releases on the project website, which will also be distributed to trade journals in the aeronautics and composite manufacturing sectors.
 - Preparation of brochures with a generic outline of the project, its benefits and the format of use for potential collaborators and end-users.

- **Publication of articles:** The Project Dissemination Manager will prepare a range of project texts that may be freely disseminated by the beneficiaries throughout Europe and beyond. These texts will summarise the objectives, activities and expected exploitable results; the practical applications; how the results might be exploited or used for future research; the need for further development work or collaborations; and project contact details. It is the projects’ aim to author some papers in high-impact peer-reviewed journals and industry-specific magazines, promoting the developments in composite materials, manufacturing and automation and processing simulation and modelling. Articles will be prepared as the project results are identified and validated and sufficient evidence is developed to satisfy the peer review process. Targeted online and print publications are given in **Table 3**.
- **Dissemination among CoPropel member organisations,** TWI is a member-based organisation with more than 150 industry members from the marine sector including major European companies such as GKN and Airbus. Using the project’s case studies and field demonstrations and the validation of the results, the project will disseminate project achievements to the aerospace and composite manufacturing community through TWI’s regular updates to the membership including publications such as the TWI Journal, and TWI industry updates. Dissemination through TWI membership also provides access to professionals in other industries that may benefit from the project outputs such as the energy, marine and automotive sectors.
- **Scheduled short training courses:** These will train the technical staff from within partner organisations, focusing on how to use the developed training tools and modules to enhance the industrial and commercial application of the project’s results.
- An invitation will be sent to at least one **CoPropel workshop**, to disseminate results to other organisations who have expressed an interest in the project. The workshop will target researchers on composite manufacturing technologies as well as industrial end users (e.g. marine, automotive manufacturers, aerospace OEMs and maintenance industries) interested in novel composite manufacturing with high throughput.
- **Coordination with other EU and national projects,** identified as relevant to CoPropel, especially those in the Horizon Europe programs.
- **Coordination with European, national and regional trade associations and technology networks** to make their members aware of the development of the project, gather interest and aid use of the CoPropel technologies down the supply chain.

Table 3 Relevant academic journals and trade publications for the communication of CoPropel project results

Academic Journals	Trade Publications
Additive Manufacturing	Composites’ World
Materials and Design	Composites Manufacturing Magazine
Advanced Manufacturing: Polymer & Composites Science	Reinforced Plastics magazine
Applied Composite Materials	

All partners are responsible for communicating project results in local and international press (press releases in magazines and newspapers, newsletters, etc.) and via EC communication channels (e.g. Horizon the EU Research and Innovation Magazine, research EC results magazine, research EC focus, etc.). These publications will be in the form of papers in scientific journals and conferences, press releases or newsletters in magazines and newspapers, etc. The partner leading the dissemination task will maintain an overview of all published results and, in cooperation with the project coordinator, will intervene if results that have been classified as publishable, do not receive the necessary diffusion. All communication activities will be approved by the project management team subject to protection of IP and commercial and contractual interests as described in the consortium and implementation agreements.

2.2. Approval/objection process of communication activities

All consortium partners are encouraged to report the results of each communication activity immediately after they are presented. One main point of contact for each partner will be made available. This point of contact will be responsible for validating and authorising any communication document before it is published. Each consortium partner should indicate the responsible person to validate and authorise any external communication among the WP leaders. External communication should be agreed by consortium WP leaders. During the life of the project and later, all the communication activities need to be approved by the consortium WP leaders and stored in a repository. Any document that needs to be shared in the public domain will be sent to the technical coordinator of the project. The technical coordinator will share it with the consortium and the topic manager for approval. As soon as it is approved, it can be published. The time for approval will be two weeks from the day that the document is shared with the consortium and coordinator.

2.3. Promotion channels

Project results will be shared inside the consortium via an online repository. In addition, they will be communicated in local and international press, in consortium partner websites; via EC communication channels as well as in exhibition and conference presentations. These channels have been chosen to promote communication, in an effective manner, of knowledge and technologies developed through the CoPropel project across the entire European Composites and marine material science Community.

2.4. Policy for communication material

All the material communicated as an outcome of the CoPropel project must include the following:

A sentence that reads as follows: This activity is part of the CoPropel project, which has received funding from Horizon Europe, the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement Number 101056911.

2.5. Branding policy

Communications from CoPropel project will be in English. The template for presentations should include the Horizon Europe undertaking logo, the grant agreement number and European Union emblem to acknowledge the funding body. The logos and the specific branding information is available at the Horizon Europe website or at the UOI sharepoint https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/logos_downloadcenter/

2.6. Public website and social media

A project website has been created and will be maintained by TWI. This website provides public information to potential stakeholders on project aims and successes. The domain selected for the project is <https://www.CoPropel.com> and a screenshot from the website is shown in **Figure 1** as follows:

Figure 1 Website for CoPropel

The website consists of six sections as illustrated below:

- Objectives and impact: This section provides a detailed description of the CoPropel project, the objectives and its impact.
- Services: The main activities that will be developed from the CoPropel consortium are: knowledge, prototype, tooling, access to market, IP generation.
- Consortium: This section lists all parties involved in CoPropel and a short description of their background and area of expertise, along with a link to their main webpages and Logos.
- Media: This is a section in the website where any reports/newsletters/articles or any other information relating to the project can be found. This is another means of communicating the project activities to a wider audience.

© MON, 26 SEPTEMBER, 2022

Brunel Composites Centre (BCC) is delighted to announce its participation as associate partner in the Horizon Europe funded CoPropel project (Grant Agreement Number 101056911) which kicked-off on the 24th of June 2022. The CoPropel project aims to develop ship propellers that are lighter, more energy

Figure 2 Media page for the CoPropel Project

A LinkedIn account was created that mirrors information shared on the website to increase visibility and reach a larger audience. The LinkedIn URL is: <https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/copropel>

Figure 3 LinkedIn URL for CoPropel

A Twitter account was also created and mirrors information shared on the website to increase visibility and reach a larger audience. The twitter URL is: <https://twitter.com/CoPropel>

Figure 4 Twitter URL for CoPropel

A linktree has also been created with all the links [@CoPropel | Twitter | Linktree](#), with the official website and the social media pages <https://linktr.ee/copropel>.

2.7. Mailing lists

The entire mailing list for CoPropel is available at the share point

[CoPropel Contact List.xlsm](#)

2.8. Logo

A dedicated logo which is the visual identity of the project has been created. The logo is illustrated in **Figure 5**

Figure 5 CoPropel logo

3. Dissemination and exploitation strategy

Dissemination is a significant tool that will be used to inform people (i.e. consortium members, the general public and specific target groups of stakeholders in the related scientific fields) of the achievements and activities performed within this project. Exploitation activities involve all actions related to the use of the knowledge generated within the project. Consequently, by effectively and strategically disseminating and exploiting the project’s results, greater public awareness is created, as well as knowledge sharing, transparency and education being promoted.

A tailored, dedicated plan for the dissemination and exploitation of CoPropel results has been prepared and is detailed below. A policy of wider dissemination of the project results will be pursued. LRT will champion dissemination of information, particularly for the purpose of ensuring future exploitation. Moreover, general dissemination activities will include:

- The inclusion of project results in the Partners and Topic Manager’s web sites.
- The publication of project results in technical papers, trade journals and conferences.
- Disclosure of information through a project brochure to relevant associations and organizations.

This draft plan summarizes the consortium’s strategy and concrete foreseen actions (to be performed during and beyond the end of the project) to disseminate, exploit and protect the new knowledge produced within CoPropel. The dissemination champion is expected to play an essential role both in the definition and implementation of this dissemination plan using his own network towards factory partners in fabrication and OEMs. The scientific knowledge developed will be disseminated to the target end-users through established links fostered by large beneficiary partners within the consortium. The target audiences and dissemination activities are listed in **Table 4**.

Table 4 CoPropel Dissemination Strategy- Target audience and means of engagement

Target audience	Format	Activity	Distribution	Deliverable
Inter-consortium communication	Email, meetings	Weekly Status Reporting, reviews	Weekly to Project team and Stakeholders	Weekly and monthly reports
European Commission	Meetings, emails	Continuous reporting of status, 2 project reviews and reporting	Project manager and EC	Status Report
Scientific community	Research publication, Conferences, workshops, emails, website	Technical information review	Six monthly to Project participants, scientific community	Technical design package
Educators	Training documents, workshops	Training reviews	As required to Project Team and Stakeholders	Training material and report
Marine and manufacturers Professionals	Emails, website, interactive forums, workshops, implementation of the	Project results reviews, updates	Quarterly to Professionals	Project outcomes: Website, interactive forums, workshops

	methods and the tools into commercially available software			
General public	Website, newsletters, leaflets, posters	Project updates	General public	Website, newsletters, leaflets, posters, electronic bulletins

3.1. Dissemination and exploitation objectives

The primary objective of the CoPropel Dissemination and Exploitation Plan is to prudently identify and organize the activities to be performed in a timely manner, in order to maximize its influence. At the same time, it will also take into account the dissemination needs of the project at each stage of its lifecycle, as well as the specific technical, market, organizational issues and interests of each of the various pre-defined CoPropel target groups/end users. Consequently, the main aims of the planned dissemination and exploitation approach can be summarized as follows:

- **Inform** about the CoPropel activities to stimulate the participation of SMEs, Academia, Industry, Research Establishments, civil society and their networks. Organise (participate in) events, workshops and seminars;
- **Raise Awareness:** Present the project, its main objectives and expected impact (e.g. CoPropel public website, social media pages, project leaflet, poster and newsletter, etc.);
- **Networking:** Exchange experiences with other projects relevant to CoPropel in order to combine efforts, minimize duplication and maximize its exploitation potential;
- **Disseminate Knowledge and make the toolset commercially available to industry:** Regularly provide information about CoPropel results through several channels (e.g. Horizon Europe, the EU Research and Innovation Magazine);
- **Support CoPropel Exploitation:** Pave the way for a successful exploitation of the project’s results by addressing the full range of potential users and uses, including research, commercial, investment, social, environmental, policy making, setting standards, skills and educational training.

3.2. Exploitation content

Exploitation activities involve all actions related to the use of the knowledge generated within the project. Through the effective and strategic dissemination and exploitation of the project results, greater public awareness is created, as well as knowledge sharing, transparency and education. The exploitation of results achieved during the CoPropel project, will enhance the relationship between the consortium partners and increase business opportunities for future applications with Tier 1 end users. Results achieved during the project will lead innovation in marine propeller product design and marine composite manufacturing processes and enhance the development of the competences and capabilities of the European marine industry.

4. Market outlook

The CoPropel consortium has prepared a draft post-project exploitation plan for the technology developed in the project. This high-level analysis of the state of the target market is intended to support the ongoing development of the plan.

The scope of this report is to assess the characteristics and growth forecasts for the project's target market, namely marine propeller manufacturing. It also examines the influence of policy and regulation, and the competitive landscape of the target market.

4.1. Status of target markets:

Marine freight shipping

The state of the marine freight markets is a fair indicator of the state of the overall economy. Since 2020 and the advent of the Covid-19 pandemic, the global economy has faced unprecedented headwinds. Currently, these include the risk of escalation of the conflict in Ukraine, rocketing energy and food prices, political instability and double-digit inflation. All this is causing a negative effect on consumer spending, either retail or B2B.

Amid fears of a global recession, consumer confidence is low and fewer goods are being bought, therefore less marine freight space is needed. DHL reports that though the shipping companies' order books remain strong the cost of freight has been falling for several months. Furthermore, since freight shipping remains a profitable enterprise, the drop in freight prices is attributable to factors outside the sector, namely the sluggishness of consumer spending due to rising interest rates and the advent of recession.

Status of target markets: Shipbuilding

It takes up to three years to build a container ship, so matching building new capacity with anticipated demand is challenging, particularly in the current era of unforeseen global shocks like the Covid-19 pandemic. This trend is exacerbated by shipbuilders' historic tendency to use profits to build new shipping capacity, thereby leading to over supply. This is undoubtedly a contributory factor to the current drop in freight costs. In 2023, 2.34 million Twenty feet Equivalent Units (TEUs) will be brought to market, 2.83 million TEUs in 2024, comfortably the largest amount of capacity ever to be built.

Researchandmarkets.com's latest analysis of the marine propellers market growth prospects predicts that the segment will grow at a rate of 4.5% per year out to 2027. Report by generic market research firms such as this one should be treated with some caution. They tend to predict a straight line upward growth trajectory, underplay the influence that external economic conditions have on a given market segment, and often disregard its particular characteristics, such as those discussed above. In this case however, given the huge increase in shipping capacity coming online in 2023-24, the growth prediction of 4.5% may be reasonably accurate.

4.2. The influence of policy and regulation

CO2 reduction

Like other heavy CO₂ emitting industries, there is now considerable pressure being applied to ship makers, owners and operators to clean up the shipping industry. Although international shipping was not included in the 2015 Paris Agreement, the International Maritime Organisation (IMO) has taken a leading role in setting out the path to zero CO₂ emissions from global shipping within this century. The Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI) for new ships, and Ship Energy Efficiency and Management Plan (SEEMP) for the existing fleet are the main policy instruments. The EEDI regulations include the need for reducing vessel weight which will inevitably involve the introduction of components made from lighter materials, such as carbon fibre composite propellers.

Noise reduction

In 2014 the IMO introduced its first policy on reducing underwater noise and its negative impact on marine life. The policy does not refer to composite propellers, but the American Bureau of Shipping, in its white paper on this topic, does, stating that

“These types of propellers may be significantly lighter, and the propeller blades can be elastically tailored to improve performance. Compared with metallic propellers, composite propellers may offer acoustic and efficiency advantages.”

Qualification and certification of composite propellers

In 2015, ClassNK, the Japanese ship classification organisation released guidelines titled Guidelines for Composite Propellers (Part on Manufacturing/Product Inspection). The guidelines arose from R&D with Nakashima Propeller and specify

“...the requirements for the approval of the manufacturing process for composite propellers and the testing/inspection of the product in the form of guidelines to assist in the effective use of composite material propellers on ships.”

In 2020, Bureau Veritas issued Guidance Note NI 663 Propeller in Composite Materials which

“...defines the procedures and requirements for certification, design, construction, installation, test, trials and surveys of composite propellers to be fitted on board ships classed with the Society.”

Both sets of guidelines indicate the growing acceptance and maturity of composite propellers in the industry. As demand for these components grows and new companies, hitherto unknown in the industry, such as composite designers, enter the market, these guidelines will provide critical quality assurance throughout the supply chain.

5. Competitive landscape

5.1. Supply chain and market entry points

In order to understand where the CoPropel technology will be targeted, a theoretical supply chain model is presented below in Figure 6. This model helps understanding of the value-adding stages, activities and actors involved in taking a major component from functional design (TRL 4-6) through to at-scale manufacture (TRL 9).

Figure 6: CoPropel theoretical supply chain model

At the conclusion of the project CoPropel technology is expected to have advanced to TRL 7 (system prototype in an operational environment, via sea trials), but is not fully market ready. When it is, it will address the central design and manufacture stage of the supply chain. To get to that point in a live commercial/industrial context may need further investment and industrial partnership.

6. Competitive landscape

The principal incumbents in the market for marine propellers are listed in **Table 5**. Those that use composite materials are asterisked and hyperlinked.

Table 5 Principal propeller manufacturers

AB Volvo
Balti Composite Technology (formerly AIR Fertigung-Technologie GmbH)*
Brunswick Corporation
Hyundai Heavy Industries
Kawasaki Heavy Industries Ltd.
LoireTech*
MAN Energy Solutions SE
Méca*
Mecklenburger Metallguss GmbH
Mercury Marine
Metstrade*
Mitsubishi Heavy Industries Ltd.
MOTH
Nakashima Propeller Co. Ltd.*
Naval Group*
Pirhana*
ProPulse AB* (no website available)
Rolls-Royce Holdings
Schaffran Propeller + Service GmbH
Schottel GmbH
Teignbridge Propellers International Limited
Veem Ltd.
Wartsila

7. Porter – five forces analysis

Supplier power – low

- Competitive due to numerous materials suppliers.
- CoPropel's materials requirements are standard.
- Switching suppliers to get better deals easy.

Threat from new entrants – low

- Few new entrants join market due to high capex costs of metal casting.
- However, threat could escalate rapidly due to the introduction of a disruptive technology e.g. CoPropel

Buyer power - High

- Large ship builders add capacity at the top of the market, creating 'boom and bust' cycles out of step with wider economic cycle.

Threat of substitution – low

- No direct competitor that combines composite propeller with integral SHM capability

Overall degree of competitive rivalry – low

- CoPropel has 'first mover' advantage

References

American Bureau of Shipping, 2021. Whitepaper: Practical considerations for underwater noise control. Available at <https://ww2.eagle.org/content/dam/eagle/publications/whitepapers/underwater-noise-control-whitepaper-21011.pdf> Accessed 20 November 2022

Bureau Veritas, 2020. New guidance note for propellers made of composite materials. Available at <https://marine-offshore.bureauveritas.com/magazine/new-guidance-note-propellers-made-composite-materials> Accessed 18 November 2022

Bureau Veritas, 2020. Propeller in composite materials. Available at https://erules.veristar.com/dy/data/bv/pdf/663-NI_2020-10.pdf Accessed 22 November 2022

ClassNK, 2015. ClassNK to releases world-first Guidelines on Composite Propellers [press release only. Full document behind paywall. Press release available at https://www.classnk.or.jp/hp/en/hp_news.aspx?id=1578&type=press_release&layout=1 Accessed 21 November 2022

DHL, 2022, Ocean freight market update, November 2022 Available at <https://www.dhl.com/content/dam/dhl/global/dhl-global-forwarding/documents/pdf/glo-dgf-ocean-market-update.pdf> Accessed 17 December 2022

The European Commission, 2019. ‘Horizon 2020 – Work Programme: 2018-2020 General annexes.’ Available at https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/wp/2018-2020/annexes/h2020-wp1820-annex-ga_en.pdf Accessed 18 November 2022

Freightwaves.com, 2022. “Container-ship building spree not over yet; new orders still rising.” Available at <https://www.freightwaves.com/news/container-ship-building-spre-is-not-over-yet-new-orders-still-rising> Accessed 17 November 2022

International Maritime Organisation, [no date]. Initial IMO GHG Strategy. Available at <https://www.imo.org/en/MediaCentre/HotTopics/Pages/Reducing-greenhouse-gas-emissions-from-ships.aspx> Accessed 21 November 2022

International Maritime Organisation, 2019. Ship noise. Available at <https://www.imo.org/en/MediaCentre/HotTopics/Pages/Noise.aspx> Accessed 21 November 2022

International Maritime Organisation, 2014. Guidelines for the reduction of underwater noise from commercial shipping to address adverse impacts on marine life. Available at <https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/MediaCentre/HotTopics/Documents/833%20Guidance%20on%20reducing%20underwater%20noise%20from%20commercial%20shipping..pdf> Accessed 21 November 2022

Marketandmarkets.com, 2022. Marine Propellers - Global Market Trajectory & Analytics. Available at https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/5030109/marine-propellers-global-market-trajectory-and?utm_source=BW&utm_medium=PressRelease&utm_code=5zxdcw&utm_campaign=1711087+-+The+Worldwide+Marine+Propellers+Industry+is+Projected+to+Reach+%246.5+Billion+by+2027&utm_exec=jamu273prd Accessed 18 November 2022

Standardclub.com, 2021. Decarbonisation in shipping: Overview of the regulatory framework. Available at <https://www.standard-club.com/knowledge-news/decarbonisation-in-shipping-overview-of-the-regulatory-framework-3919/> Accessed 21 November 2022